

1 Current Guidelines for Menopausal Disorders Do Not Specify Reassessment Timing for
2 Ineffective Hormone Replacement Therapy

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14 Conflict of Interest:

15 The author reports that his child is employed by Nippon Zoki Pharmaceutical Co.,
16 Ltd., a company that manufactures and markets analgesic products, including tramadol,
17 acetaminophen, tramadol/acetaminophen combination tablets, and Neurotropin®.

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19 **Abstract**

20 Hormone replacement therapy (HRT) is widely used to treat menopausal disorders.
21 The International Menopause Society, British Menopause Society, and National Institute
22 for Health and Care Excellence guidelines describe the expected time frame for
23 symptom improvement. However, these guidelines do not specify the timing of
24 discontinuation, modification, or reconsideration of alternative diagnoses when HRT
25 provides minimal or no symptom improvement. Some patients continue HRT for more
26 than six months despite minimal or no symptom improvement. This paper highlights the
27 absence of standardized reassessment timing for HRT and argues for the establishment
28 of expert consensus-based provisional criteria. In general, pharmacotherapy involves
29 treatment modifications, such as dose escalation, discontinuation, or switching to an
30 alternative agent, when the therapeutic effect remains inadequate after a defined period.
31 However, in HRT for menopausal symptoms, the timing for determining an inadequate
32 response and subsequent management remain unclear. Widespread pain, fatigue, and
33 sleep disturbances are common features of several clinical conditions, including somatic
34 symptom disorder, fibromyalgia, myofascial pain syndrome, and menopausal disorders.
35 Because, hormone levels in menopausal women often fluctuate markedly and may fall

1 outside the normal reproductive-age range, it remains clinically challenging to
2 determine whether these symptoms are due to hormonal changes. HRT is associated
3 with serious adverse effects, including thromboembolic events. Continuing treatment
4 despite insufficient symptom improvement may prolong exposure to these risks and
5 delay the identification of alternative diagnoses and appropriate treatments. The efficacy
6 of HRT is best evaluated based on improvement in subjective symptoms rather than
7 achievement of hormone levels within the reproductive-age range. Although it is
8 difficult to provide a clear evidence-based recommendation for the timing of HRT re-
9 evaluation, the development of provisional expert consensus-based benchmarks,
10 potentially using the Delphi method, may help prompt treatment modification,
11 reconsideration of differential diagnoses, support patient safety, and reduce potential
12 risks.

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14 **Key Words:**

15 hormone replacement therapy, menopausal disorders, guidelines, fibromyalgia,
16 thromboembolic events, treatment failure

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19 Hormone replacement therapy (HRT) is widely used to treat menopausal disorders.
20 The International Menopause Society (IMS) recommendations describe the expected
21 time frame for symptom improvement ⁽¹⁾. However, the IMS⁽¹⁾ and British Menopause
22 Society (BMS) ⁽²⁾ recommendations, along with the National Institute for Health and
23 Care Excellence (NICE) guideline ⁽³⁾, do not specify the timing of discontinuation,
24 modification, or reconsideration of alternative diagnoses when HRT provides minimal
25 or no symptom improvement. Clinical observations suggest that some patients continue
26 HRT for more than six months despite experiencing minimal or no symptom
27 improvement. These observations highlight a potential pattern; however, future
28 case-series studies are required to confirm its generalizability. This paper aims to
29 highlight the absence of standardized reassessment timing for HRT and to argue for the
30 establishment of expert consensus-based provisional criteria. However, it does not seek
31 to evaluate the validity of the diagnostic classification itself.

32 In general, pharmacotherapy involves treatment modifications—such as dose
33 escalation, discontinuation, or switching to an alternative agent—when the therapeutic
34 effect remains inadequate after a defined period. However, in hormone replacement
35 therapy (HRT) for the treatment of menopausal symptoms, the timing for determining

1 an inadequate response and the appropriate subsequent management remain unclear.

2 Widespread pain, fatigue, and sleep disturbances are common features of several
3 clinical conditions, including somatic symptom disorder, fibromyalgia, myofascial pain
4 syndrome (MPS), and menopausal disorders. Although hot flashes and excessive upper-
5 body sweating are typical features of menopausal disorders, their absence does not
6 exclude the diagnosis. Conversely, the presence of these symptoms does not exclude
7 somatic symptom disorder, fibromyalgia, or MPS; therefore, the differential diagnosis
8 among these conditions remains challenging. Because hormone levels in menopausal
9 women often fluctuate markedly and may fall outside the normal reproductive-age
10 range ⁽⁴⁾, similar hormonal fluctuations may be observed in asymptomatic or mildly
11 symptomatic individuals. Therefore, it remains clinically challenging to determine
12 whether these symptoms are due to hormonal changes.

13 HRT is associated with serious adverse effects, including an increased risk of
14 thromboembolic events ⁽¹⁾. Continuing treatment despite insufficient symptom
15 improvement not only prolongs exposure to these risks but may also delay the
16 identification of alternative diagnoses and appropriate therapeutic interventions. In the
17 author's clinical experience, patients initially diagnosed with menopausal disorders are
18 subsequently diagnosed with fibromyalgia or chronic widespread pain, with symptom
19 improvement after appropriate treatment for fibromyalgia. Conversely, some patients
20 diagnosed with fibromyalgia fail to respond to standard fibromyalgia therapies but
21 experience symptom improvement with HRT.

22 The efficacy of HRT is best evaluated based on improvement in subjective symptoms
23 ⁽⁵⁾. In contrast, achieving hormone levels within the reproductive-age range is not an
24 appropriate criterion for assessing treatment response.

25 It is difficult to provide a clear evidence-based recommendation for the timing of
26 HRT re-evaluation. However, without explicit guidance on HRT re-evaluation intervals,
27 HRT may be continued for prolonged periods even when subjective symptoms do not
28 improve. Where evidence is insufficient, the Delphi method is widely used
29 internationally. In the context of HRT for menopausal disorders, it would be valuable for
30 academic societies (specialist organizations) to take the lead in developing expert
31 consensus using this approach to propose provisional benchmarks for HRT re-
32 evaluation timing. Even without robust evidence, establishing a practical guide based on
33 such benchmarks could help prompt treatment modification and the reconsideration of
34 differential diagnoses, thereby supporting patient safety and reducing potential risks.

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